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Research Article

LEVELS OF ALT AND PLATELETS COUNT AMONG NON- WORKING PRIMIGRAVIDA GROUP WOMEN AS COMPARE TO WORKING PRIMIGRAVIDA WOMEN

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Abstract:

Introduction: Preeclampsia is one of the major health problems during pregnancy. It complicates 3%–8% of pregnancies and causes marked increase in perinatal, maternal morbidity, and mortality. Although the exact pathophysiology of preeclampsia is not completely understood, certain factors have been attributed to it, which include deficient trophoblastic invasion of the maternal vascular bed with subsequent reduction of placental blood flow. **Aims and objectives:** The basic aim of the study is to analyze the levels of ALT and platelets count among non-working Primigravida group women as compare to working Primigravida women comparatively. **Methodology of the study:** This was a randomized control study conducted in Shifa International hospital Islamabad during July 2019 to November 2019. We collected the data from 78 female patients who visits the OPD of a hospital. We divided the data into two groups one was those who were non-working Primigravida group women and second group was working Primigravida group. We collected all the basic characteristics of selected patients of both groups. We recorded their Hb levels, BMI and mean Alt levels for the analysis of liver function in pregnant women. **Results:** The data were collected from 78 patients with the mean age of sedentary life primigravida women are 26 ± 3.5 and regular exercising primigravida women are 27.4 ± 2.5 . BMI of working women was noted as 26.4 ± 2.4 and in non-working women as 24.12 ± 2.1 . Results shows that Hb level of working women becomes high as compared to non-working women. The mean level of ALT in non-exercising women are 45.6 ± 10.2 i.u/dl and in regular exercising women are 28.41 ± 7.4 i.u/dl. **Conclusion:** It is concluded that working regular light exercise may reduce the chances of HELLP syndrome and pregnancy induced increased ALT.

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INTRODUCTION:

Preeclampsia is one of the major health problems during pregnancy. It complicates 3%–8% of pregnancies and causes marked increase in perinatal, maternal morbidity, and mortality. Although the exact pathophysiology of preeclampsia is not completely understood, certain factors have been attributed to it, which include deficient trophoblastic invasion of the maternal vascular bed with subsequent reduction of placental blood flow¹. Primigravida (PG), defined as a woman who conceives for the first time, is in a high-risk group². PGs are at significantly higher risk for prolonged first and second stage of labor, increased chances of fetal distress during labor and need for intensive monitoring as compared to the multigravidas³. PGs are also at significantly increased risk for operative vaginal delivery and emergency cesarean section. The chances of primary postpartum hemorrhage in PGs are found to be more, and perinatal morbidity is also increased in the group⁴. Higher PC is associated with cardiovascular disease and vascular complications as a result of its role in inflammation and thrombosis; also, platelet activation is observed in people with diabetes, hypertriglyceridemia, and insulin resistance⁵. Diabetes, hypertriglyceridemia, and insulin resistance are strongly associated with MS, and previous studies have found that PC is also elevated in patients with MS after adjustment for age, gender, ethnicity, and total cholesterol⁶.

Placental under perfusion initiates widespread systemic, maternal endothelial dysfunction, and increased vascular permeability. Coagulation system is activated by the contact of platelets with the injured endothelium leading to increase in consumption as well as bone marrow production of platelets⁷. Various indices are used to measure platelet functions, for example, the platelet count (PC), mean platelet volume (MPV), the PC to MPV ratio, and platelet distribution width (PDW); PDW measures platelet size distribution⁸. The utility of different platelets indices as predictors of

preeclampsia has been studied previously; however, reports in this regard are controversial⁹.

Aims and objectives

The basic aim of the study is to analyze the levels of ALT and platelets count among non-working Primigravida group women as compare to working Primigravida women comparatively.

METHODOLOGY OF THE STUDY:

This was a randomized control study conducted in Shifa International hospital Islamabad during July 2019 to November 2019. We collected the data from 78 female patients who visits the OPD of a hospital. We divided the data into two groups one was those who were non-working Primigravida group women and second group was working Primigravida group. We collected all the basic characteristics of selected patients of both groups. We recorded their Hb levels, BMI and mean Alt levels for the analysis of liver function in pregnant women. Non probability convenient sampling method was used on the basis of inclusion and exclusion criteria.

The collected data were analyzed using SPSS software (version 17). The results are presented as a mean with 95% confidence interval limits or standard deviations. The significant value for $P < .05$ was accepted as statistically significant.

RESULTS:

The data were collected from 78 patients with the mean age of sedentary life primigravida women are 26 ± 3.5 and regular exercising primigravida women are 27.4 ± 2.5 . The mean Hb level were differ significantly in working and non-working women, as mean Hb level is 10.5 ± 2.31 and 12.4 ± 2.6 among working and non-working women respectively. BMI of working women was noted as 26.4 ± 2.4 and in non- working women as 24.12 ± 2.1 . Results shows that Hb level of working women becomes high as compared to non-working women. The mean level of ALT in non-exercising women are 45.6 ± 10.2 i.u/dl and in regular exercising women are 28.41 ± 7.4 i.u/dl.

Table 01: Analysis of levels of Hb and ALT levels in both groups of selected patients

Characteristics	Sedentary life Primigravida	Regular exercising primigravida	P Value
Maternal age (years) mean	26±3.5	27.4±2.5	.005
Gestational age in weeks mean	27.4 ± 2.21	26 ± 3.6	.005
BMI mean	26.4± 2.4	24.12 ± 2.1	.002
Mean Platelet count (1000/ μ L)	216.34 ± 12.33	271 ± 33.45	.001
Mean Hb (% , w/w)	10.5±2.31	12.43±2.6	.001
Mean ALT level i.u/dl	45.6 ± 10.2	28.41 ± 7.4	.001

Comparison of levels of MPC, Hb and mean ALT in non-working Primigravida group women with working Primigravida women on the basis of mean values

DISCUSSION:

Our results show that those women who do exercise and physically active have more good results as compared to others. We looked for two variables like ALT and platelets count, in primigravida women. In this study we depend the result on EXERCISE in one group and non-exercise 2nd group. These two variables found and compared in both groups. We found that ALT of exercising group was lower and platelet count higher, but in sedentary life group primigravida, ALT have lower value and platelets counts were lower which leads to the risk for HELLP syndrome.

Pregnancy is the normal incident in the life of a woman body, every pregnancy is a unique experience for women and each pregnancy the women experience will be new and adequately different from the previous¹⁰. The anatomical and physiological changes in pregnancy are associated with minor discomforts between women during pregnancy. Self-management regarding minor discomforts and practices during prenatal period is beneficial for pregnant women so practices of women about self-management are necessary for their health protection. Pregnancy induced hypertension is thought to be one of the major causes of maternal death and sufferings all over the country¹¹.

CONCLUSION:

It is concluded that working regular light exercise may reduce the chances of HELLP syndrome and pregnancy induced increased ALT.

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